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Implementation of an InceptionV3 network with an LSH index for
image similarity search

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1.0 Introduction

The purpose of this project is to test the ability of a pre-trained neural network, in particular the network InceptionV3, to correctly classify a set of images for which the network was not trained after being correctly fine-tuned and in presence of a distractor dataset, whose aim is to try to induce the network to return wrong results if not robust enough. To perform the matching over the features extracted through our network, we will implement from scratch an LSH index, which is used to fasten the matching process. In order to have a complete study, we will compare the performances of the classification using the fine-tuned network and the standard version of the network, as well as testing the performances with and without the distractor.

In the second chapter, we will give a fast overview of the four main components of this project, which are the network, the index, the dataset and the distractor. We will then present, in the third chapter, our implementation, explaining in detail the choice we've made. In the fourth chapter we will compare the results obtained in the different tests, while in the fifth chapter we will present a simple user manual for our web interface. Finally, in the sixth chapter we will draw the conclusions for our project.

2.0 Components

In this section, we will give a brief overview of all the components of our project: in particular, we will give some information about the neural network we use in this project, InceptionV3; we will also show the theory behind LSH; finally, we will explain in details the study we performed over the dataset and the distractor.

2.1 InceptionV3 Network

InceptionV3 is a convolutional neural network developed by Google and broadly used in image analysis, object detection and in the computer vision field in general. It is part of a family of neural networks called Inception networks, whose aim is to create a powerful network with as few parameters as possible in order to decrease the complexity of the network while still obtaining very good results in terms of object classification: in particular, this network uses around 21 million parameters, which is around one third of the parameters exploited by AlexNet, which has 60 million parameters. This aspect is particularly interesting in Inception networks: if we look at the comparison between this network and the other most popular networks over the classification on the ImageNet dataset, we can see that the original version of Inception is able to achieve an incredibly high performance in terms of accuracy, exploiting ten times less parameters than its counterparts and using a way lower number of Floating Point Operations (FLOP) for a forward pass:

Comparison					
Network	Year	Salient Feature	top5 accuracy	Parameters	FLOP
AlexNet	2012	Deeper	84.70%	62M	1.5B
VGGNet	2014	Fixed-size kernels	92.30%	138M	19.6B
Inception	2014	Wider - Parallel kernels	93.30%	6.4M	2B
ResNet-152	2015	Shortcut connections	95.51%	60.3M	11B

The peculiarity of the Inception architecture is that it uses multiple kernels of different size within the same layer: in particular, the InceptionV3 architecture is divided in ten Inception blocks or modules, which are sets of layers exploiting different kernels working in parallel, whose results are compared at the end of the corresponding Inception block in order to choose the best kernel size for each block. This approach is taken since in image

classification is not easy to decide the optimal size for the kernel, since large kernels are able to detect global features in an image, while small kernels would be able to recognize specific details: using this parallel approach, Inception is able to recognize both and perform a high level object classification, capturing salient features at different kernel sizes.

2.2 LSH Index

Locality-Sensitive Hashing (LSH) is a particular type of indexing technique exploited for approximate similarity search in a metric space: this approach exploits the idea of collisions in hash functions, which are encountered when two different objects are associated by the same hash function to a single hash value. Although generally we try to avoid collisions in classical approaches that use hash functions (storage of sensitive data, compression algorithms and so on), in this case we want to have collisions: in particular, we want two objects that are similar, therefore close in the metric space, to have the same hash value, which can be pictured as a bucket inside which the object's id is stored. In order to do this, LSH exploits a function $g()$ which is the composition of multiple hash functions $h()$: the idea is that each hash function $h()$ applied to an object gives as result the projection of the point over a randomly generated, segmented vector, in particular returning the index of the segment on which the projection falls; the $g()$ function then returns a list of indexes computed through the various $h()$ functions, which will identify the bucket to which the object will be associated:

As we can see from the picture, the algorithm tries to associate with a certain probability the same bucket to points which are close in the metric space: the higher the number of hash functions h , the smaller the probability of two close objects to stay in the same bucket, but at the same time the smaller the dimension of the bucket itself. Notice that

by using a single $g()$ function, it is possible to have a set of vectors which are not able to correctly divide the objects: it is always a good practice to use multiple $g()$ functions and merge the final results together, in order to avoid losing possible good candidates for the final result, eliminating the duplicates or exploiting them to understand the likelihood of two objects to actually be close one to the other.

The original LSH was proposed for binary vectors, in particular for problems in which we use the Hamming distance to compare binary vectors. In this approach, the feature vectors corresponding to the objects are represented as bits of fixed length: each $h()$ function in this approach corresponds to a certain position on the vector, which simply returns the value of the vector in said position; the $g()$ function is again the concatenation of all $h()$ functions:

□ $p_1 = \langle 1, 0, 0, 1 \ 0 \rangle$	$g(p_1) = \langle 0, 1 \rangle$
□ $p_2 = \langle 0, 0, 0, 1 \ 0 \rangle$	$g(p_2) = \langle 0, 1 \rangle$
□ $p_3 = \langle 1, 0, 0, 1 \ 1 \rangle$	$g(p_3) = \langle 0, 1 \rangle$
□ $p_4 = \langle 0, 1, 1, 1 \ 1 \rangle$	$g(p_4) = \langle 1, 1 \rangle$

As we can see, by using this approach, objects that are similar one to the other will fall in the same bucket with a high probability, even if there's a small chance that objects which are not too similar (like p_2 and p_3) fall in the same bucket as well: again, in order to have a more reliable result, we can use multiple $g()$ functions and merge the results together as we said for the generalized LSH.

For our project, we've implemented and tested both the solutions, as it will be shown later on in this document.

2.3 Birds-315 Dataset

Birds-315 is a dataset that can be found on Kaggle which contains 50,582 images of birds divided in 325 classes corresponding to 325 different species. The original dataset is also divided into training images (47,332, at least 120 images for each species, but the number of images per species is not perfectly balanced), test images (1625, 5 for each species) and validation images (1625, 5 for each species). All the images have size 224x224x3 and have jpg format. Since the test and validation images from the dataset were hand-

selected to be the “best” images for testing the network, which would include a bias in the final result, we decided to ignore the original splitting of the data and perform our custom splitting over the whole set of images, randomly taking 80% of the images as training set, 10% of the images as test set and 10% of the images as validation set but still preserving the distribution of classes in all the sets: this also allows us to create a model which is more accurate on unseen or in general new images, making it also more robust to the distractor.

One significant problem of the dataset is that it doesn't have a balanced amount of pictures between male and female birds inside each species: male birds are typically more colored while female tends to have blander colors, but since the dataset has a small amount of images from female birds we may incur in incorrect classification; a possible solution could be to oversample the female images in order to balance the distribution of males and females, but the dataset doesn't have any annotation about the sex, so it is not possible to perform this optimization and we have to use the dataset as is.

2.4 MirFlickr-25000

MirFlickr-25000 is a dataset containing 25,000 pictures associated with metadata and tags and related to a diverse set of concepts and features. In our case, we will use this dataset as a distractor for the trained network: in particular, our aim is to create a robust network which is able not to be “fooled” by the distractor, correctly classifying bird images as it should and giving low scores to unrelated images coming from the distractor. The result set of the similarity search therefore should not include any image coming from the distractor, but actually include only pictures of the same bird species.

3.0 Implementation

In this chapter, we will show the implementation of our project, using some snippets of code to highlight the main decisions we took. We will also give a brief overview of the organization of the Drive folder we've used, along with the division of the Colab notebooks we adopted.

3.1 Drive organization

The Drive folder we've used is divided into different sections, each one containing one particular element of our project:

- In the “Dataset” folder it is possible to find the original Birds-315 dataset we've worked on, along with the MirFlickr-25000 dataset: these have been saved in order to achieve a faster and simpler retrieval inside the notebooks;
- The “Datasets_metadata” folder contains the CSV files of the target dataset, which has been divided into training, test and validation sets, and the distractor. The “Birds” subfolder actually contains the original division of the dataset, whose authors proposed on Kaggle; the “train_test_split” folder contains instead the version of the training, test and validation sets we used, saved in here in order to have replicable results among the different tests we performed;
- The “Descriptors_FineTuning” and “Descriptors_NoFineTuning” contain, respectively, the descriptors of the distractor and the training, test and validation sets extracted from the fine-tuned network and from the not-fine-tuned network. Each set of descriptors has been saved directly from Google Colab in .npy format, which can be easily loaded later on in other notebooks: this allows to avoid the recomputation of the descriptors each time we need to perform a test, saving an important amount of time and allowing replicable results;
- The “Kaggle” folder contains the “kaggle.json” token to download the dataset from Kaggle;
- The “Models” folder contains the models we're using in our project: instead of performing the training and the fine-tuning each time, we can simply load the models from here;

- The “Notebooks” folder is the main folder we use and contains all the notebooks we’ve exploited to create our projects. The notebooks are connected one to the other by importing the different notebooks inside the one we’re interested in. The “GettingData.ipynb” notebook contains the code that has been used to extract and save the descriptors from the dataset and from the distractor, along with a small test in which we perform a 10-NN search on a randomly selected query, showing visually the images corresponding to the results; the “FineTuning.ipynb” notebook contains instead the training of the classifier on top of the Inception network and the fine-tuning of the network for the optimized model, along with a simple preprocessing on the data to be fed to the network in the correct way and the extraction of the descriptors using the fine-tuned model. In the “LSH.ipynb” notebook we defined our LSH index, in particular we both defined a binary version of the LSH index and a non-binary version, which are both tested in a subsequent notebook: this notebook also includes all the utilities for the creation of the index, insertion of an object and querying. The “Performance.ipynb” notebook contains the tests we have performed to understand the mean average precision and query time of our index, which are reported in chapter 4, while the “Performance_Plots.ipynb” notebook contains the plots of the results obtained in the “Performance.ipynb” notebook. Finally, in the “REST” subfolder, we have two notebooks that have been created to develop our user interface, which is deeply documented in chapter 5;
- The “Performance” folder contains the results as a set of .npy files, where each one corresponds to the list of solutions obtained during the performance tests, saved in order not to always perform the same test which can be highly time-consuming;
- The “Results” folder contains the visual results of our tests, in particular it contains for each test a screenshot of the mAP and average duration along with some queries and the complete picture with the results for all the queries.

3.2 Feature extraction and data preparation

The first step of our project has been to download the datasets and the network in order to extract the descriptors to be used by the LSH index. In particular, we decided to extract the descriptors from the predefined sets offered by the Birds-315 dataset, then merge

them together and perform the `train_test_split` function over them, using a 80-10-10 split for, respectively, training, test and validation set. For the extraction of the features, we had first to resize the images: in fact, the dataset offered 224x224x3 images, while the InceptionV3 network works on 299x299x3 images, so we had to resize to the latter resolution in order to obtain the best results from our network. After resizing, we preprocessed the images using the `preprocess_input()` function of the InceptionV3 network, using the result to extract the descriptor. The following snippet of code shows the extraction process performed on all the sets, distractor included:

```
def extract_descriptors(filepaths):
    descriptors = []

    for path in tqdm(filepaths):
        image_data = tf.io.read_file(path) # read image file
        image = tf.image.decode_image(image_data, channels=3, expand_animations=False)
        image = tf.image.resize(image, (299, 299)) # resize

        image = np.array(image)
        image = np.expand_dims(image, axis=0) # add batch dimension
        image = image.astype(np.float32)

        image = tf.keras.applications.inception_v3.preprocess_input(image)
        image_descriptor = network.predict(image)
        image_descriptor = image_descriptor.squeeze() # tf.Tensor to numpy array
        descriptors.append(image_descriptor)

    return descriptors
```

3.3 Definition of the model and training of the classifier

The following step of our project was to build a classifier and train it on top of the frozen layers of the InceptionV3 network. The model we created is composed by 5 layers, according to the model summary:

- The first layer is the “data_augmentation” layer, which we introduced in order to avoid overfit due to the considerable size of the InceptionV3 network: in particular, in this layer we perform a horizontal flip, a rotation and a zoom;
- The second layer contains the pre-trained network, which is made by 10 inception blocks as explained in paragraph 2.1. This is exactly the same network, which has been loaded along with the ImageNet-based weights and without the pre-trained classifier;

- The third, fourth and fifth layers are dense layers, where the third layer has 1,024 units, the fourth layer has 512 units and the fifth layer has 325 units, equal to the number of classes of our dataset. The size of the layers has been chosen in order not to reduce too quickly the size of the output of the last layer of the InceptionV3 network, which produced 2,048 channels in input: we noticed that using just the classifier layer or too few units in general would decrease significantly the output, so we inserted two dense layers each one with half the units of the dimension of the precedent output. We also used two dense layers instead of a single one in order to increase the non-linearity and the modelling capabilities of the network, which has resulted in better performance. The third and fourth layer use a ReLU activation function, while the final layer exploits a softmax function in order to assign probability-based scores.

Layer (type)	Output Shape	Param #
sequential_4 (Sequential)	(None, 299, 299, 3)	0
inception_v3 (Functional)	(None, 2048)	21802784
dense_6 (Dense)	(None, 1024)	2098176
dense_7 (Dense)	(None, 512)	524800
dense_8 (Dense)	(None, 325)	166725
=====		
Total params: 24,592,485		
Trainable params: 23,553,349		
Non-trainable params: 1,039,136		

We then defined an Adam optimizer with learning rate equal to 0.0001: it is important to notice that we started with a value of 0.001, which proved to be too high since we were reaching the plateau over the validation set but the accuracy was ranging from 65% to 70%; we therefore tried to run a small grid search, using values of the learning rate around 0.0001, which in the end proved to be the best learning rate. We finally compiled the model using as loss measure the sparse categorical cross-entropy and as metric the accuracy:

```

tf.keras.utils.set_random_seed(7)
pretrained_network.trainable = False

data_augmentation = tf.keras.Sequential([L.RandomFlip("horizontal"),
                                         L.RandomRotation(0.1),
                                         L.RandomZoom(0.2),])

model = tf.keras.models.Sequential([
    data_augmentation,
    pretrained_network,
    tf.keras.layers.Dense(1024, activation='relu', name='classifier_hidden1'),
    tf.keras.layers.Dense(512, activation='relu', name='classifier_hidden2'),
    tf.keras.layers.Dense(number_of_classes, activation='softmax')
])

opt = tf.keras.optimizers.Adam(
    learning_rate=0.0001,
    name='Adam'
)

model.compile(loss="sparse_categorical_crossentropy",
              optimizer=opt,
              metrics=["accuracy"])

```

At this point, we performed the training over 10 epochs for the model in order to train the classifier, using also a shuffling technique to shuffle the training set at each epoch not to present the images always in the same order. The final results of the training are shown in the following pictures:

As the pictures show, we've been able to achieve a remarkable result on the accuracy for the validation set, arriving at a plateau and without having overfitting or underfitting. Further increasing the number of epochs proved not to be useful since the validation loss started increasing from that point on: this model achieved an 87.7% accuracy on the test set as well.

3.4 Fine-tuning InceptionV3

Taken the best model from the previous training, we performed fine-tuning on the model by unfreezing some layers: in particular, since the InceptionV3 network is formed by inception blocks, we performed multiple tests fine-tuning the network from each inception block, adding also regularization in order to reduce the complexity of the network and therefore further reducing the probability of overfitting. In particular, we applied an L2 regularization by adding a penalty of 0.001 to the layers, in order to avoid large weights which could be the result of the notable depth of the network. We therefore performed the tests by switching between non-fine-tuned and fine-tuned models, trying different depths for fine-tuning, different sizes of the images (224x224x3 and 299x299x3), with and without regularization and data augmentation: the model which performed the best according to these tests was the model fine-tuned from block 9 onwards, so starting from layer 249, using 299x299 images and exploiting both data augmentation and regularization, able to achieve an accuracy over the test set of 91.4%. It is important to highlight that the data augmentation technique was able to improve the accuracy, but of less than one percentage point, and so did the regularization; the difference between the usage of 224x224x3 images and 299x299x3 was instead significant, with an increase on the use of the latter from 3 to 5 percentage points. Finally, we noticed that fine-tuning from deeper blocks was actually giving slightly worse results than fine-tuning from block 9 onward.

3.5 LSH Index

As already mentioned in paragraph 2.2, we decided to implement both types of LSH index, for which the general workflow is similar but it differs in the actual implementation: first of all, we use a function named `create_index()`, which takes as arguments the number of `g` functions, the number of `h` functions for each `g` function and the number of dimensionalities of the vectors in the database, returning the set of `g` functions that will be used to create the hash of each descriptor, with the idea of creating different `g` functions to ensure we don't lose similar images due to a particular positioning of the vectors in the space. The `create_index` calls a `create_hash_function()` function, which has the following code:

```

def create_hash_function(k, d, binary, w=4, mean=0, std=1):
    """
    Arguments:
        k(int) is the number of h functions
        d(int) is the dimensionality of vectors x(i)
        binary(bool) to indicate binary LSH
        w(float) is the weight (default=4) [only if binary is false]
        mean and std(float) are the parameters of the gauss distribution [only if binary is false] (default=0 and 1 respectively)

    Returns:
        A hash family g such that:
        if binary --> returns g=[i(1),...,i(k)] where i is a random index in range (0, d)
        else --> returns g=[[x(1), w(1), b(1)],..., [x(k), w(k), b(k)]]
    """
    if binary:
        #Sample k indices between 0 and d without replacement
        rand_index = np.array(random.sample(range(0, d), k))
        #Sort the sampled indices
        rand_index.sort()
        return rand_index
    else:
        #def [x(1),...,x(k)] random vectors from gauss distrib
        x = [np.random.normal(mean, std, d) for i in range(0, k)]
        #def [b(1),...,b(k)] random scalars
        b = np.random.uniform(0, w, k)
        #return g = [[x(1), w(1), b(1)],..., [x(k), w(k), b(k)]]
        g = [[x[i], w, b[i]] for i in range(0, k)]
        return g

```

This function creates all the g functions and corresponding h functions: using the parameter “binary”, we can either decide to create a binary index or a non-binary index. In case of binary index, what we do is simply take k random indexes in the range of the dimensions of the vectors to be used as hash functions to build the buckets; in the non-binary case, we create k vectors from a random distribution with mean equal to 0 and standard deviation equal to 1, that are then used as parameters for the h functions to compute the hash of the descriptors, along with the biases, which are computed for each h function as a random sample between 0 and w, which is considered equal to 4 as suggested in the original paper presenting the LSH index.

Once that the functions to build the index has been created, we can compute the hash value of each descriptor using a function called `index_database()`, which takes as input the number of g functions, the number of h functions and the list of object descriptors to index, which are actually vectors of size (1, d). For each object descriptor, an `insert_object()` function is called, which is defined as follows:

```

def insert_object(G, p, binary):
    """
    Arguments:
        G is the index represented as a list of hash families [g(1),...,g(l)]
        p(tuple (id, descriptor)) is the database object
        binary(bool) to indicate binary LSH
    Inserts an object identifier p(id) inside buckets=hash(p(descriptor)) for every g family
    """
    #for each g(i), compute_hash(g(i), p) then insert in bucket g(p) [file] the identifier of p
    for i in range(0, len(G)):
        bucket = compute_hash(G[i], p[1], binary)
        if not os.path.exists(str(i)):
            os.mkdir((str(i)))
        f = open(str(i)+"-"+bucket,"a+")
        f.write(str(p[0]))
        f.write('\n')
        f.close()

```

At this level, the binary and non-binary functions still work in the same way, computing the hash value of the descriptor and inserting the id of the corresponding object in the computed bucket: note that, since we use multiple g functions, we first create a folder for each g function given by the index of the g function in G, which is the list of g functions retrieved from the create_index() function; inside each folder, we then store a file for each bucket, where the name of the bucket is equal to its hash value for the corresponding g function. At this point, the way we compute the bucket is different between the binary and non-binary case: in the binary case, we extract the values of the descriptor in position equal to the corresponding h functions, as explained in 2.2, concatenating them together to obtain the final value of the bucket; in the non-binary case instead, for each h function in g we compute the value to be used to create the bucket:

```

def compute_hash(g, p, binary):
    """
    Arguments:
        g is a hash family = list of hash functions h = [[x(1), w(1), b(1)],..., [x(k), w(k), b(k)]] if binary is false
        = list of random indecies i = [i(1),...,i(k)] if binary is true
        p(vector (1xd))is a database vector
        binary(bool) to indicate binary LSH
    Returns:
        bucket(string): The hash value of the object p computed as:
            floor((x.p + b)/w) if not binary
            p[i(1),...,i(k)] if binary
    """
    bucket = ""
    if binary:
        #extract the binary values of the indecies
        vals = p[g]
        #create a binary string from those values
        bucket = ''.join(map(str, vals))
    else:
        #compute the dot product between x and p for every x in every hash function h and concatenate the results in a string
        for h in g:
            bucket += str(int(abs((np.dot(np.array(h[0]), p)+h[2])/h[1])))
    #return the hash value
    return bucket

```

The formula to compute the bucket is the following:

$$h_i(P) = \lfloor (p \cdot X_i + b_i) / x \rfloor$$

At this point, the index is created and ready to be queried: in order to query the index, we have defined a `get_knn()` function, for which, given a query, the database, a list of `g` functions and the number of neighbors `k` we want to find, we retrieve the list of the `k` nearest neighbors:

```
#compute_hash(q) for each g(i) in G then retrieve the list of id inside each bucket
buckets=[]
for i in tqdm(range(0, len(G)), disable=test):
    bucket = compute_hash(G[i], q, binary)
    if not path.exists(str(i)+"-"+bucket):
        continue
    f = open(str(i)+"-"+bucket, "r")
    objects = f.readlines()
    f.close()
    buckets.append(objects)

#flatten the retrieved ids
retrieved_objects = [obj for sublist in buckets for obj in sublist]
#create a set to remove duplicate ids
retrieved_objects = set(retrieved_objects)

#convert the set into an np array
retrieved_objects = np.array([int(retrieved_object) for retrieved_object in retrieved_objects])

#return from the function if nothing was retrieved
if retrieved_objects.size==0:
    return retrieved_objects

#compute the real distances between the retrieved objects and the query
# if binary, compute the hamming distance
# if not binary, compute the euclidean norm
descriptors = database[retrieved_objects]
if binary:
    distances = np.count_nonzero(np.logical_xor(q, np.array(descriptors)), axis=1)
else:
    distances = np.linalg.norm(q - np.array(descriptors), axis=1)

#return the ordered list of objects
rank = distances.argsort() #ascending scores
return retrieved_objects[rank]
```

To retrieve the `k` nearest neighbors, we first compute for each `g` function the bucket in which the query would be placed: we then take all the ids contained in each bucket to create a list of retrieved objects. Since there is a very high probability to have ids which are replicated among the retrieved buckets, we need to remove duplicates and to do this we simply transform the retrieved list into a set, that is then again converted in a numpy array for easier handling. At this point, given our array of retrieved objects, we compute the real distances between the descriptors of the objects and the query, which are then sorted and finally returned as the ordered array of similar objects, from which just the first

k objects are taken as k nearest neighbors. Of course, the computation of the distance is different between the non-binary and the binary case: in the binary case, we compute the Hamming distance between the query and the descriptors, using a simple XOR; in the non-binary case, we compute the distance as the Euclidean norm between the query and the descriptors. Finally, notice that if the size of the list of retrieved objects is zero, we simply return an empty list, which needs to be handled correctly when computing the mAP to study the performance of the algorithm.

It is important to highlight a final aspect: when using the binary LSH index, we need the database to contain binary descriptors, which is not the case for our situation; moreover, the query as well needs to be in binary form. To solve this problem, we implemented a `binarize()` function: in this function, the first thing we need to do is to compute the mean vector, which is the mean vector of the vectors of the database; this vector is used to binarize the database, in particular for each vector of the database we perform component-wise comparison with the mean vector, assigning to the binarized version of the corresponding vector a 0 in the studied position if the value of the vector for that position is lower than the value of the mean vector for the corresponding position, 1 otherwise. This function is used to compute the binarized database and returns the latter along with the mean vector: the mean vector is returned so that it can be used during querying, since otherwise we would have to recompute it from scratch:

```
def binarize(database, mean_vector=None, test=False):
    """
    Arguments:
        database(matrix(nxd)) is the database to binarize
        mean_vector(vector(1xd)) to use a reference mean to binarize or to generate it if None(default)
        test(bool, default=False) to indicate whether or not to display tqdm progress bar (if True, don't display it)

    Returns:
        binarized_database(binary matrix (nxd))
    """

    #to be used for the training set
    if mean_vector is None:
        #calculate the mean vector of the database if it's not specified in the arguments of the function
        mean_vector = database.mean(axis=0)
        binarized_database = []
        #for every vector in the database, do component-wise comparison with the mean vector and assign 0 if a component is
        #less than the corresponding component in the mean vector and assign 1 otherwise
        for vector in tqdm(database, disable=test):
            binary_vector = [0 if vector[i] < mean_vector[i] else 1 for i in range(len(vector))]
            binarized_database.append(binary_vector)
        #return the binarized database
        return np.array(binarized_database), mean_vector

    #to be used for the queries/test set
    else:
        #do the component-wise comparison with the passed mean vector and apply the same policy as before
        binarized_database = []
        for vector in tqdm(database, disable=test):
            binary_vector = [0 if vector[i] < mean_vector[i] else 1 for i in range(len(vector))]
            binarized_database.append(binary_vector)
        #return the binarized database
        return np.array(binarized_database)
```

As we can see, during training we pass the entire database to compute the mean vector; during querying, we don't actually pass the database but we only pass the query (or a set of queries during testing), so we need to pass the mean vector for the comparison.

4.0 Comparison of the results

We tested different versions of both the index and the feature extractor and we measured the performance in terms of mean Average Precision and average query time. We considered the first 100 elements of the test set as our query images for the performance measurement. For the feature extractor we considered the version without fine-tuning and the fine-tuned version that previously achieved the best accuracy. For the index, we considered a binary implementation and a non-binary implementation. The binary one computes a mean vector of the dataset features and then compares each feature vector with the mean: it produces a new feature vector that has 0s for the components that have a lower value in the original feature vector than in the mean feature vector, and has 1s for the components for which the opposite is true. For the index we also considered two parameters: the number of hash functions to use (g), and the number of h functions to use for each hash function. For each combination, we found the best values for these two parameters.

We evaluated the performance using the mean Average Precision, which expresses how many relevant results are retrieved on average for a query. To compute this value we provide a ground-truth for the dataset, stating a-priori which elements are relevant for a certain query, based on their labels. We also used the average query time as a performance metric, which is measured by recording the query time for each individual query and then by computing the average:

```
aps = []
for i in range(0, n_queries):
    ranked_relevance = groundtruth[i, retrieved[i]]
    relevant_items = ranked_relevance.sum()
    precision = ranked_relevance.cumsum()
    prec_at_i = []
    for j in range(1, ranked_relevance.size+1):
        x = precision[j-1]/(j)
        prec_at_i.append(x)
    prec_at_i = np.array(prec_at_i)
    if relevant_items == 0:
        aps.append(0.0)
    else:
        aps.append((ranked_relevance * prec_at_i).sum() / relevant_items)
aps = np.array(aps)

return aps
```

In order to compute the mAP, we first compute the Average Precision on the set of retrieved elements: in particular, given our groundtruth, we compute the precision at k as

saw in the laboratories, considering Average Precision equal to 0 in case we don't retrieve any relevant item with our knn query, while in case we retrieve less than k relevant item we don't assign a 0 for the missing item, but we penalize the miss during the computation of the precision at k.

The following table is a summary of the measurements described above. Every experiment described in this chapter was executed on Google Colab with the "Performance" notebook:

Dataset	Fine-tuning	Binary LSH	Best g value	Best h value	mAP	Average query time (s)
Birds	NO	NO	10	1	0.8088	0.3612
Birds	NO	YES	9	6	0.8261	0.1583
Birds	YES	NO	7	1	0.9166	0.0457
Birds	YES	YES	5	5	0.9155	0.0425
Birds and Distractor	NO	NO	10	1	0.8089	0.5978
Birds and Distractor	NO	YES	10	5	0.8461	0.4989
Birds and Distractor	YES	NO	6	1	0.9150	0.0636
Birds and Distractor	YES	YES	8	9	0.9182	0.0188

The best results are obtained when the network is finetuned and the binarization is applied, both with and without the distractor. We can see that both the average query time and the mean Average Precision are improved by the fine-tuning in all scenarios. As we can see, the performances are almost the same when adding the distractor to the

database, therefore we can say that we've been able to achieve a good robustness for our network. Furthermore, choosing the best g and h parameters in each situation, we manage to obtain better results when the distractor is added, even if we might expect the opposite outcome. In the "Results" drive folder it is possible to find the outputs of all the experiments, both entirely reported with a png image, and inside a shorter screen.

5.0 Web Application

We developed a simple web application that allows users to perform a similarity search on an arbitrary image. The image is uploaded in the application, which then responds with the ten nearest neighbors retrieved using the index that we developed. The application uses the index parameters that achieved the best results in our experiments, as well as the fine-tuned feature extractor that achieved the best results.

5.1 Application Structure

The web application consists of two main modules:

1. A REST Server written in python and directly deployed on Google Colab.
2. A Web Application developed in C# within the Blazor framework, that acts as client for the REST Server.

All the necessary files for this part of the project are included in the Drive folder, precisely in “Notebooks/REST”. There are two python notebooks: the first one, called “REST_Server”, is used for running the actual API Server, which is defined in the python file “app.py”, while the other one, called “REST_Support”, is just an interface with the LSH notebook, that provides the functions related to the index management and querying.

The REST Server uses the Flask python library in order to provide a single API endpoint. The endpoint is routed at “<server_address>/findKNN”, and accepts POST requests. The requests must contain a json parameter called “image”, which is a string containing the base 64 representation of the query image. The response provided by the server contains a json structure that looks like this:

```
{
  "neighbors": [
    [<label>, <base64_image_representation>],
    ...
    ...
    [<label>, <base64_image_representation>]
  ]
}
```

The response includes an array of ten (or less, if ten are not found) neighbors for the query image, and for each neighbor the label and the base 64 representation are provided, so that they can be displayed on the client.

The application client can be executed on any device connected to the internet, since it only needs the server's IP address in order to work. It is a simple Blazor Server Side application, based on the ASP.NET Core framework. When the user uploads an image, the application sends a request to the API endpoint described above and waits for the response. After the response is received, the retrieved neighbors are displayed.

The client application is actually hosted on a server in the house of a group member and is accessible via the internet.

5.2 User Manual

The following steps are required to run the application:

1. Open the "REST_Server" notebook on Google Colab (<https://colab.research.google.com/drive/16UINj1p2ex6H-c9D7iLrz6fDbOCMYegZ?usp=sharing>);
2. Run all the cells;
3. Wait for the last cell to display a similar text:

```
-----  
* Serving Flask app "__main__" (lazy loading)  
* Environment: production  
  WARNING: This is a development server. Do not use it in a production deployment.  
  Use a production WSGI server instead.  
* Debug mode: off  
* Running on http://127.0.0.1:5000/ (Press CTRL+C to quit)  
* Running on https://meaningful-roy-assumed-paxil.trycloudflare.com  
* Traffic stats available on http://127.0.0.1:8099/metrics
```

If it doesn't display it after a while, click on the input bar and press enter a few times, this should immediately show the desired output;

4. Copy the link containing "*trycloudflare.com*", which will be the url of the REST Server;
5. Try opening the link: you should see a white page with "Welcome to Golab REST API" written in the top left corner. If you see an error instead, wait for 30 seconds and try again;

- Open any web browser and go to the address <http://gbeccari.ddns.net:10420>. You should see this:

- Click on the gear icon on the right, an alert will open. Insert the server address copied in step 4 and click “OK”;

Running a query is very simple:

- Click on the Choose File button. A pop-up window will appear to browse the filesystem of the device.
- Select any .png or .jpeg image and click on the “Open” button in the bottom right corner of the window.
- Wait for the response to be displayed. You should see your query image and ten or less neighbor images right below it, with their label. It should look like this:

6.0 Conclusions

The implementation of the LSH index over descriptors extracted through InceptionV3 has led to very good results, as we can see from the performance chapter: it is though interesting to make some final observations on the results we obtained, in particular looking at the file stored in “Results” folder of our Drive. By looking to the queries, it is clear how the network is able to recognize similar shapes, but has difficulties in recognizing colors, as we can see in the picture below:

Although being very different in color, the birds shown above in the first picture have a very similar shape, from which the network incorrectly supposes they all are the same species; in the second picture, it is clear that less weight is given to the color, while the shape is correctly recognized. This problem is present in many queries and is the reason why the overall accuracy, even if very high, can't increase too much: this problem is also quite important in bird classification, since very often birds of the same species differ by color between male and female. A possible solution to this problem would be to use a network which gives the same importance to color and shape during feature extraction, or to use LIFT or similar color-texture feature extraction methods in order to obtain better descriptors and finally a better performance of the network.

A similar situation also happens for flying birds, which are almost all incorrectly classified: this may be due again to the high relevance given to the shape of the bird with open wings, which is recognized as a species with such particular trait; another possible reason for this to happen is that the number of pictures of flying birds in our dataset is very small compared to the number of pictures of non-moving birds, so the network just considers all these pictures as birds of the same species.

It is important to highlight some results of the performance tests: the best mAP in the non-binary case is always achieved using one single h function, independently from the number of g functions used, since using multiple h functions often result in many buckets with few items, which lower the Average Precision as explained above. Moreover, binary LSH always seems to outperform non-binary LSH both in mAP and average query time, even if no particular patterns can be found in choice of h and g from our tests.

Along with our main project, we inserted some commented snippets of code which has not been tested but may be interesting for further studies: for example, we've tried to develop an LSH index in which, if the number of retrieved objects from a set of buckets is lower than need, we can study similar buckets (therefore buckets which are close in value to the target bucket) and retrieve their objects in order to obtain as many objects as needed. This version would slightly increase the average query time since more buckets will be accessed, but it could also improve the accuracy and perform very well using many g functions. Many other possible implementations and optimizations are therefore possible and may be of interest for subsequent studies.